

Leveraging the Semi-supervised Learning Method UniMatch V2 for the Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge

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we leverage the application of the semi-supervised learning method UniMatch V2, integrated with the DINOv2 model, to tackle the Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge. UniMatch V2 is a semi-supervised learning method that builds upon the self-supervised DINOv2 model, which excels at generating high-quality feature representations from unlabeled data. By incorporating a unified data augmentation strategy and complementary channel-wise dropout, the proposed method significantly enhances model performance while reducing computational costs. We conduct extensive experiments comparing the performance of UniMatch V2 with other well-established models, such as UNet, UNet++, and Attention-UNet. The results demonstrate that the UniMatch V2 method achieves superior segmentation performance, as indicated by higher Dice Similarity Coefficients (DSC), lower Hausdorff Distances (HD), and reduced running time, making it an effective solution for the Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge.

1 DINOv2 Model

DINOv2 is a self-supervised vision transformer (ViT) model designed for unsupervised learning tasks such as image classification and feature extraction. Building on the Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture, DINOv2 leverages a teacher-student training paradigm to generate high-quality feature representations from unlabeled data. In this study, we fine-tune the pre-trained DINOv2 model, provided by Meta, to optimize its performance for the task at hand.

The backbone of DINOv2 is the Vision Transformer, which utilizes a self-attention mechanism to process image patches. Experimental results indicate that, by capturing long-range dependencies within images, ViT achieves state-of-the-art performance across a variety of visual tasks. DINOv2 adopts a teacher-student framework, wherein two models (the teacher and the student) are trained concurrently. The teacher model is updated using an exponential moving average (EMA) of the student model's weights, ensuring the stability and generalization of the teacher's knowledge. DINOv2 is also self-trained, employing contrastive learning to maximize consistency across augmented views of the same image while minimizing consistency between different images. The data processing pipeline is shown in Figure 1, with the ViT model framework depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Overview of the Data Processing Pipeline.

Figure 2: Overview of the Vision Transformer (ViT) Model.

2 UniMatch V2

Building upon the DINOv2 model, we introduce the UniMatch V2 method for semi-supervised training. UniMatch V2 represents an enhancement over the original UniMatch method. In this updated version, the ResNet backbone from UniMatch has been replaced with the higher-performing DINOv2 model as the encoder. Additionally, the dual data enhancement stream from UniMatch has been replaced with a unified single-stream data augmentation process, improving performance while reducing training costs. This modification stems from the observation that the loss incurred from purely feature-level augmentations is marginal compared to that from input-level augmentations, thus the feature-level augmentation stream was eliminated.

Furthermore, UniMatch V2 introduces Complementary Channel-Wise Dropout. In this configuration, two strongly augmented images are randomly generated, and random Dropout is applied to their respective features during decoding, thereby enhancing model performance. The UniMatch framework is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Evolution from FixMatch (a) to UniMatch V1 (b), and finally to UniMatch V2 (c).

3 Experiment

3.1 Experimental setup. In this experiment, the learning rate for the parameters of the backbone is set to 0.000005, while the learning rate for the other parameters is set to 0.0002. The crop size is adjusted to 518, and the confidence threshold (conf_thresh) is set to 0.95. For the pre-trained DINOv2 model, we utilize the small version.

3.1 Experimental Results. To evaluate the performance of the UniMatch V2 method with the

DINOv2 model, we compare the results with other models, including UNet, UNet++, and Attention_UNet. The experimental results are presented in Table 1.

	DSC	HD	Running Times(s)
UNet	0.8218	53.3176	84.3871
UNet++	0.8041	53.9993	205.8126
Attention_UNet	0.8288	56.9050	188.6776
DINOv2	0.8486	34.3002	23.6367

Table 1: Comparison of Experimental Results using UNet, UNet++, Attention_UNet, and DINOv2.

4 Conclusion

The results presented in the above experiments demonstrate that the semi-supervised learning method, employing the UniMatch framework with the DINOv2 model as the encoder, outperforms traditional models such as UNet, UNet++, and Attention_UNet. The improvements in performance suggest that UniMatch V2, combined with DINOv2's advanced feature extraction capabilities, provides a highly effective approach for the task at hand.